

DIGITAL PRESERVATION

in Diamond Open Access publishing

In the digital age, publications are vulnerable to technology failures, platform changes and format obsolescence, while Diamond Open Access publishers face significant challenges. Learn key strategies to ensure the long-term preservation, interoperability and accessibility of published articles.

ARCHIVE YOUR PUBLICATIONS

DARK ARCHIVES

Services like [LOCKSS](#), [CLOCKSS](#) and [Portico](#) are robust, distributed archiving systems that safeguard your content and provide continued access if your primary platform fails or is discontinued.

COMMUNITY GUIDANCE

Diamond Open Access publishers can face significant resource challenges in digital preservation, but you can get support from community initiatives like the [PKP Preservation Network](#) for [Open Journal Systems](#) users, and [Project JASPER](#) for Diamond OA Journals indexed in the [Directory of Open Access Journals \(DOAJ\)](#).

PREPARE FOR ARCHIVING

CONTENT

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Fonts: Unicode-compliant, open-source.

Images: high-resolution with descriptive captions.

Tables: easy to interpret, well-structured, annotated.

Consistent file naming: follow best practices.

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Metadata: machine-readable in widely used formats. eg. XML, CSV, JSON.

Open and widely used file formats like PDF, HTML and EPUB.

PDF is not optimal for small screens or text and data mining.

Tag full-text in **XML JATS or equivalent** (e.g. TEI).

Use **multiple formats**.

FORMATS

